

CITIZENS' ASSESSMENT ON PROGRAMS FOR EDUCATION OF THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNIT OF BANGA, AKLAN

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ABSTRACT

Citizen Satisfaction Index System (CSIS) was used to assess the delivery of support to education initiatives in the municipality of Banga, Aklan, Philippines. The samples were determined using multiple application of stratified random sampling approach. In accordance with the Philippine Statistical Authority's Data on Census Population and Housing for 2015, barangays having a bigger share of the population contributed more respondents to the 150 targeted participants. Following the inclusion criteria, the probability respondents were chosen using the Kish Grid. Pre-numbered questionnaires were distributed, with odd numbers targeting male responders and even numbers targeting females. The following criteria were used to evaluate the respondents' assessments: awareness, availment of the program/service, satisfaction, and need for action. Furthermore, interviews were conducted to better understand and investigate the respondents' thoughts, behavior, and perspectives. The reasons for their reaction were also obtained. The data was provided in percentage as well as frequency distributions. The study inferred that awareness on alternative learning system and/or special education program should be improved since it is the only program that attained low rating for awareness. Most of the residents were not able to avail education programs because they have no household member who attends school. Majority of the respondents who availed the services were satisfied. However, scholarship and other assistance programs to students may be enhanced to improve service delivery. It is highly recommended by the citizens to improve accessibility to scholarship programs and other forms of financial assistance to students.

Keywords: CSIS, education programs, assessment, local government, citizen feedback

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INTRODUCTION

Banga is a third-class municipality in the Philippine province of Aklan. It has a total of thirty-one (31) public schools that offers Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) and one Higher Education Institution (HEI). The Banga Local Government Unit has been a consistent recipient of the Department of Interior and Local Governance's Seal of Good Local Governance (SGLG) Award which is awarded to LGUs that has notable performance in the delivery of programs including support to education services. The various services are spearheaded by the different units with mandates relevant to the service. In this study, the programs under Environmental Management were the focus of the study.

Citizen Satisfaction Index System (CSIS) was used to assess the delivery of support to education initiatives in the municipality of Banga, Aklan, Philippines. CSIS was developed as a system of methods to generate citizen feedback on local government service delivery performance and citizen satisfaction (Yecla & Ortega 2020). It is a system intended to collect and obtain valuable citizen feedback on the performance of local governments' service delivery and citizens' overall satisfaction. The CSIS conceptualizes the citizen as the center of local government performance.

The CSIS data serve as a guide for local governments in establishing policies and managerial decisions related to their goal of providing basic services to the population. It can assess the pulse of the people in order to be responsive to a larger portion of the population. The information can reinforce decisions on policies and programs that center on services that are regarded to be deficient and those that have a strong impact on citizen satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study was to assess the performance of the Local Government Unit of Banga, Aklan in providing support to education initiatives. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic information of the respondents in terms of
 - a. whether the respondents' household members are enrolled in elementary or secondary school,
 - b. the grade level of the household members who have studied in the previous 12 months and now,
 - c. if the household member is enrolled in public or private schools, and
 - d. the main reason why household members attended public schools?
2. What is the respondent's assessment of the following educational assistance services:
 - a. medical and/or nutritional benefits rendered at school clinics
 - b. programs and services in sports,
 - c. scholarships and other student aid programs
 - d. Special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System?
3. What are citizens' recommendations to enhance education programs?

RESEARCH METHOD

Respondents. The target respondents were 150 voting-age people (18 years and older) who had resided in the different barangays of Banga for at least six months. Because it is the most populous barangay, barangay Linabuan Sur received the most responses (15). This barangay yielded three sample locations. Poblacion and Pagsanghan each had ten responders.

Sampling Procedures. Multi-stage random probability selection was used to select 150 sample-respondents. This type of sampling draws a sample at random from a population in various stages or phases. This method is categorized in the stratified random sampling. The sampling process included the following stages:

Stage 1. Based on the PSA's 2015 Census Population and Housing data, the intended 150 respondents were distributed proportionally in every barangay. Thirty sample locations, such as a public shed, basketball court, health center, and/or multi-purpose pavement, were identified in each barangay.

Stage 2. Each sample households were identified by determining the sample spot that served as the starting point. The starting sample household was identified by determining the number of houses suggested by the random start (RS). Following the identification of the first household, an interval utilizing the number specified in the random start was used to choose the subsequent households.

Stage 3. The Kish Grid was used to choose a qualified sample respondent from each household. Female respondents were given even-numbered surveys, while male respondents were given odd-numbered questionnaires.

Research Design

The study employed a combination of quantitative and qualitative research methodologies, including face-to-face interviews with residents drawn at random from the municipality of Banga. The CSIS uses multi-stage probability sampling which is a type of sampling that draws a sample at random from a population in various stages or phases (DILG CSIS Manual, 2019). This was used to make sure that every citizen had an equal chance of being chosen as a participant in the research study, with no favoritism for any specific political and social feature, ideological inclination, or religion.

Population and Sample

There were 150 voting age adults (18 years and above) who were target respondents of the survey. They were residents of the different barangays of Banga, Aklan including the Poblacion. Table 1 displays the distribution of respondents per barangay. Out of the 30 barangays in the municipality of Banga, only 26 were included in the survey based on the population. Among the barangays included in the sample, Linabuan Sur has the highest number of 3,756 of population while the lowest was in Lapnag with 627 residents. There were 30 sample spots throughout the municipality with Barangay Linabuan Sur having the highest number of spots and the greatest number of respondents (15).

Ethical Consideration

The researchers first made a courtesy call to the mayor of Banga. The data collection in each barangay began with a visit to the Barangay Captain to request permission to conduct the study in that barangay. Before being regarded as respondents in the study, the participants were given complete information about the objective of the activity and obtained their consent. This allowed the researchers to collect valid qualitative data on sensitive issues by bestowing a shroud of confidentiality and anonymity on participants. According to the inclusion criteria, only people aged 18 and above are permitted to engage in the survey; thus, no minor respondents were involved in the study.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents per Barangay

Barangay	Population* [A] (39,505)	Number of Sample Spots [B] =[A]/ 39,505*30	Number of Spots Rounded off	Number of Respondents
1	Agbanawan	1,524	1	5
2	Bacan	1,703	1	5
3	Badiangan	1,747	1	5
4	Cerrudo	1,485	1	5
5	Cupang	740	1	5
6	DajaNorte	1,340	1	5
7	Dingle	698	1	5
8	Jumarap	1,835	1	5
9	Lapnag	627	1	5
10	Libas	1,717	1	5
11	Linabuan Sur	3,756	3	15
12	Mambog	1,803	1	5
13	Mangan	1,542	1	5
14	Muguing	764	1	5
15	Pagsanghan	1,917	2	10
16	Palale	678	1	5

17	Poblacion	1,997	2	2	10
16	Polo	955	1	1	5
19	Polocate	1,707	1	1	5
20	Sibalew	989	1	1	5
21	Sigcay	1,012	1	1	5
22	Taba-ao	1,164	1	1	5
23	Tabayon	1,777	1	1	5
24	Torralba	1,890	1	1	5
25	Ugsod	1,566	1	1	5
26	Venturanza	824	1	1	5
	TOTAL	39,505	30	30	150

Instruments

The fieldwork processes were divided into sub-processes, namely: sampling, data gathering/interviewing using a standardized research questionnaire (DILG CSIS Manual, 2019), data processing, analysis, report preparation, and completion and evaluation. After the finalizing the research results, a Utilization Conference was conducted to present the study findings to the local government unit of Banga and to translate the findings into tangible action plans to enhance the development of local services.

Data Analysis

The following are the basic principles in measuring the feedback of the respondents: 1.) Awareness refers to the existence of knowledge about the service offered by the LGU. Before delving into satisfaction, it is vital to ascertain whether they are aware that the service is provided by the LGU. 2.) Availment relates to the respondent's interaction with the programs, projects, and services that are currently being provided. This could suggest willingness among citizens to use public services. Only respondents who stated to be aware of the service would be interviewed about availability. 3.) Satisfaction is related to people's contentment with their availment of local government services. This may also reveal the citizen's appreciation with the programs to which they have access. In service indicator level assessments, only persons who have utilized the service are assessed about their satisfaction. 4.) Need for Action relates to the citizen's assessment of a certain service if it requires efforts for improvement or modification. This idea is paired with satisfaction to provide an additional dimension measure that may aid in the refinement of program prioritization for further improvement.

Frequency score was used to describe the ratio of awareness, availment, satisfaction and need for action relative to the sample or a subset of the sample while adjectival equivalents was derived by subjecting percentage scores to a 50% + MoE test and it uses a cut-off.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

a. Profile of Respondents with households' members in public schools

i. Response as to the respondents' household members are enrolled in elementary or secondary school

The data in the Table show the response as to the respondents' household members are enrolled in elementary or secondary school. Results point out that one-half (50%) of the entire population of respondents specified that they have members enrolled in either elementary or secondary schools. Another half (75 or 50%) of the respondents quantified that no one in their household is enrolled in elementary or high school.

Table 2: Response as to the respondents' household members are enrolled in elementary or secondary school

Indicator	Frequency (n = 150)	Percent
Yes	75	50
No	75	50

ii. *Grade level of the household members who have studied in the previous 12 months and at present*

The table presents the Grade level of the household members who have studied in the previous 12 months and at present. It could be picked up from the data that most (14 or 10.53%) of the household members were in Grade 8. Other respondents declared that their household members are in Grade 1 (13 or 9.77%), Grade 3 (12 or 9.02% 11.03%), Grade 6 (11 or 8.27%) and Grades 5, 7 and 10 (10 each or 7.52%). Only seven or 5.26% have household members who are in the kindergarten.

Table E3. Grade level of the household members who have studied in the previous 12 months and at present

Indicator	Frequency (n = 133)	Percent
Kindergarten	7	5.26
Grade 1	13	9.77
Grade 2	8	6.02
Grade 3	12	9.02
Grade 4	8	6.02
Grade 5	10	7.52
Grade 6	11	8.27
Grade 7	10	7.52
Grade 8	14	10.53
Grade 9	12	9.02
Grade 10	10	7.52
Grade 11	8	6.02
Grade 12	10	7.52

iii. *Response as to the classification of school (public or private schools) where the household member is enrolled*

The Table 3 presents the responses as to the classification of school (public or private schools) where the household member is enrolled. The results showed that more than three-fourths (110 or 82.71%) of the respondents had household members studying in public schools while 23 or 17.29% of them have household members studying in private schools.

Table 3. Response as to the classification of school (public or private schools) where the household member is enrolled

Indicator	Frequency (n = 133)	Percent
Public	110	82.71
Private	23	17.29

iv. *Main reason why household members attended public schools*

The table below reflects the main reason why household members attended public schools. Results reveal that 49 or 44.55% of the respondents' household members attended public school because it was near or accessible. Moreover, 45 or 40.91% of the respondents reasoned out that tuition is free. Moreover, least number (one each or 0.88%) cited the reason of being and ESC scholar, their child wants to study in the school and there was no other secondary school in the barangay, respectively.

Table 4: Main reason why household members attended public schools

Indicator	Frequency (n = 110)	Percent
Near/Accessible	49	44.55%
Libre ang tuition	45	40.91
Mababa ang tuition	3	2.73
Maganda ang kalidad ng pagtuturo	6	5.45
Maganda ang pangangasiwa ng paaralan	2	1.82
School supplies are provided for free	2	1.82
The school is near to our house	49	44.55
ESC Scholar	1	0.91

Dito gustong mag aral ng anak	1	0.91
Walang ibang High School sa barangay	1	0.91

a.1. Awareness

The overall respondents' awareness on Support to Education Services/Programs is manifested in the following Table below. Results reflect that there was a high adjectival rating for awareness on medical and/or nutritional benefits rendered at school clinics, programs and services in sports, and scholarships and other student aid programs. Special Education Programs, on the contrary, received low adjectival ratings.

Table 5: Awareness on Education Services/Programs

Program/Service	Yes	No	Total Number of Respondents	Awareness		Adjectival Rating
				Percentage Score	Cut off	
Medical and/or nutritional benefits rendered at school clinics	90	60	150	60.00%	58.00%	High
Programs and services in sports	100	50	150	66.67%	58.00%	High
Scholarships and other student aid programs	89	61	150	59.33%	58.00%	High
Special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System	75	75	150	50.00%	58.00%	Low

a.2. Availment

The table below shows the overall respondents' availment of education services/programs. It is shown that the availment in all the services indicated low adjectival rating.

Table 6: Availment on Education Services/Programs

Program/Service	Yes	No	Total Number of Respondents	Availment		Adjectival Rating
				Percentage Score	Cutoff	
Medical and/or nutritional benefits rendered at school clinics	41	49	90	45.56%	60.33%	Low
Programs and services in sports	41	59	100	41.00%	59.80%	Low
Scholarships and other student aid programs	16	73	89	17.98%	60.39%	Low
Special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System	0	75	75	0.00%	61.32%	Low

a.3. Satisfaction

The table exhibits the overall respondents' satisfaction on program, for education. Results display that there was a high adjectival rating in most of the services. However, special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System obtained small sample.

Table 7: Satisfaction with Education Services/ Programs

Program/ Service	Yes	No	Total Number of Respondents	Satisfaction		
				Percentage Score	Cutoff	Adjec tival Rating
Medical and/or nutritional benefits rendered at school clinics	38	3	41	92.68%	65.31%	High
Programs and services in sports	40	1	41	97.56%	65.31%	High
Scholarships and other student aid programs	13	3	16	81.25%	74.50%	High
Special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System	0	0	0	0%	0%	Small Sample

a.4. *Need for Action*

The table below depicts the overall need for action on educational programs. Results show that there was a high adjectival rating on Scholarships and other student aid programs. On the other hand, a low adjectival rating on medical and/or nutritional benefits rendered at school clinics and programs and services in sports was obtained. Special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System had small samples since no respondent rated such service.

Table 8: Need for Action on Education Services/Programs

Program/Service	Yes	No	Total Number of Respondents	Need for Action		
				Percentage Score	Cutoff	Adjectival Rating
Medical and/or nutritional benefits rendered at school clinics	21	20	41	51.22%	65.31%	Low
Programs and services in sports	19	22	41	46.34%	65.31%	Low
Scholarships and other student aid programs	12	4	16	75.00%	74.50%	High
Special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System	0	0	0	0%	0%	Small Sample

a.5. *Recommendation from Citizens*

The overall recommendations from the citizens on educational services/programs revealed accessibility to scholarship and other forms of financial assistance topped with 40 or 26.67%. Provision of sufficient school supplies, equipment and facilities, improvement of existing programs for education and additional budget to support these programs were recommended by 33 or 22%, 25 or 16.67% and 13 or 8.67%, respectively.

Table 9: Recommendations on Education Services/Programs

Recommendations	Frequency (n = 150)	Percent
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Accessibility to scholarship and other forms of financial assistance	40	26.67
Provision of sufficient school supplies, equipment and facilities	33	22.00
Improvement of existing programs for education	25	16.67
Additional budget to support programs for education	13	8.67
Establishment of school-based medical and dental clinic	9	6.00
Construct additional school buildings	7	4.67
Establishment of public high school in the barangay	6	4.00
Hiring of additional teachers	5	3.33
Regular implementation of feeding program	3	2.00
Upgrading of barangay primary school to elementary school	3	2.00
Enhancement of sports programs	2	1.33
Utilization of available school equipment in schools such as computers	2	1.33
Establishment of special education center in the barangays	1	0.67
Implementation of additional programs for out-of-school youths	1	0.67

Discussion

The citizens of Banga, Aklan mostly prefer to enroll or send their household members in public schools because the tuition is free. This is in consonance with the findings (Reyes et al, 2020) where the citizens of the municipality of Lezo, Aklan mostly prioritize public schools because of free tuition. Recently, the Philippine government has introduced a subsidy to cover free tuition and miscellaneous fees for Filipino students (Lim et al, 2018). It was noted that the number of enrollees in public schools including higher education institutions increased upon implementation of Tertiary Education Subsidy (TES) (Fuentes, 2021).

On the other hand, results on awareness unfolded that there is low awareness on Special education initiatives such as Alternative Learning System among all the educational services offered in the municipality. The Alternative Learning System (ALS) of the Department of Education in the Philippines is a parallel learning system that is an alternative to conventional formal education. Its goal is to give out-of-school Filipino youth and adults access to basic education (Estrada et al, 2019). Unemployed/underemployed out-of-school youths and adults, school dropouts/leavers, industry workers, stay-at-home spouses, house cleaners, factory workers, drivers, members of cultural minorities, indigenous people, PWDs, inmates, and rebels and rebel returnees are among the target beneficiaries (Apao et al, 2014). From a landscape of a division (Abad et al, 2020), high support mechanism in ALS program was small and positively low but significantly related to the teachers' highly positive attitudes towards work and the teachers' best practices in implementing the program. The Alternative Learning System program was proven to be helpful in developing the recipients' life skills (Apao et al, 2014). This was supported by the study of research findings that the ALS Program has touched lives across different socio-economic backgrounds (Ruiz et al, 2020). The government should scale-up and enhance the support mechanism directed to improving ALS program implementation in the country through considering adequate budget allotment and community encourage specially to out-of-school youth who already lost their drive to get back to schooling and others already feels shy since they were already left behind by their school age groups.

Availment resulted in a low rating. Based on the interview conducted, some were not able to avail the educational programs because some of the respondents do not need the services anymore. Other reasons noted where the respondents were not interested to participate in sports and ALS programs, and "no scholarship offered". The operation of the ALS program should be enhanced because ALS for out-of-school young people has been found to be a sound investment for poor young people (Mehra et al, 2021).

Moreover, students were found out to lack motivation to participate in sports program. This was also in consonance with the study conducted by Reyes et al in 2020 where the students have low participation to sports activities in school. Regardless of the numerous proven advantages of exercise and physical movement on physical and mental health, only a small fraction of people exercises on a regular basis, which includes active participation in sports activities (Cagas et al, 2015). Further, research shows that participation in sports increased players' judgments of academic success, mental processes, and being more logical and patient (Montecalbo-Ignacio et al, 2021). The local government of Banga, Aklan and

academic institutions in the locality should enhance programs for sports through campaign or offering inclusive sports activities to encourage participation of the citizens and promote benefits from engaging to such activities. In addition, the findings say that there were a number of citizens who were not aware of scholarship programs offered not just by the locality but by the national government as a whole. This may be an isolated case but a massive awareness campaign must be rolled out to disseminate numerous scholarship and other forms of financial assistance offered by the LGU and the national government. Those who have availed the education programs and services in municipality of Banga mostly indicated that they were satisfied by what and how programs and services are delivered to them.

Satisfaction with all the educational programs and services was high. Despite the excellent satisfaction rating, the program on scholarships and other student support programs received a high need for action. This implies that the LGU should not stop and work further on the implementation and delivery of scholarships and other assistance programs for the people of Banga. Quality assurance of any program or service must become an essential part of institutional management and planning (Ruiz & Junio-Sabio 2012). Relevant to this, it was the top recommendation of the citizens to provide avenue for scholarship accessibility to and other forms of financial assistance

CONCLUSION

A high number of the citizens prefer to enroll or send their household members in public school because the tuition is free. The citizens of the municipality of Banga are highly aware of most of the educational programs offered in the locality except on alternative learning system and/or special education program. On the other hand, citizens are satisfied with the educational programs offered in the LGU. However, interventions to enhance services on scholarship and other assistance programs to students may be considered to further improve the services, which was also the top recommendation of the citizens.

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